

NONINVASIVE VENTILATION IN PEDIATRIC ACUTE RESPIRATORY FAILURE BY
MEANS OF A CONVENTIONAL VOLUMETRIC VENTILATOR

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Title: NIV IN PEDIATRIC ACUTE RESPIRATORY FAILURE

ABSTRACT

Background: To evaluate the feasibility and outcome of noninvasive ventilation (NIV) by volumetric ventilator with specific NIV mode in pediatric acute respiratory failure (ARF).

Methods: Prospective non controlled study in children with ARF who received NIV delivered by Evita 2 Dura with NIV mode, through a nonvented oronasal mask, for three years.

Results: 32 episodes of ARF in 26 patients. Pneumonia was the most frequent diagnosis (46.8%). Pediatric logistic organ dysfunction (PELOD) score was $12.4\pm 24\%$ (range 0-84%). The highest set of parameters: peak inspiratory pressure 18.5 ± 2.7 cmH₂O (15-26); positive end-expiratory pressure 5.7 ± 1.1 cmH₂O (4-9), pressure support 10.5 ± 2.7 cmH₂O (5-18) and mean pressure 9.2 ± 2 cmH₂O (6-14). There was a progressive clinical score improvement within the first 6 hours. The following results were obtained before initiating NIV: Respiratory rate 41.7 ± 16.3 , heart rate 131.6 ± 25.8 , systolic arterial pressure 108 ± 19.5 , diastolic arterial pressure 58.2 ± 13.9 , pH 7.33 ± 0.12 , pCO₂ 55.1 ± 20.2 , SatO₂ 87.8 ± 9.9 and FiO₂ 0.55 ± 0.25 . A significant improvement in respiratory and heart rate, pH, pCO₂ and SatO₂ was reported at 2-4 hours. This improvement was maintained in throughout the first 24 hours. The FiO₂ was significantly lower at 24 hours.

Radiological improvement was observed after 24 hours in 17 out of 26 cases. The duration of NIV was 85.4 ± 62.8 hours. Complications were defined as minor. Only 4 patients required intubation. All patients survived.

Conclusions: NIV can be successfully applied to infants and children with ARF using this volumetric ventilator with specific NIV mode. It should be considered particularly in children whose underlying condition warrants avoidance of intubation.

Key Words: noninvasive positive pressure ventilation; children; acute respiratory failure; conventional volumetric ventilator; pneumonia

INTRODUCTION

Acute Respiratory Failure (ARF) is one of the main causes for admission to Pediatric Intensive Care Unit (PICU). Children with ARF frequently require endotracheal intubation (ETI) and mechanical ventilation (MV). Despite assuring patient airway and ventilation, this treatment is not free of risks and complications such as nosocomial infection, tracheal and pulmonary injury and the need for sedation.^[1,2,3,4] Noninvasive ventilation (NIV), that is to say, MV without ETI or tracheotomy, could minimize these complications^[5] and reduce length of stay in the PICU in patients who do not need airway protection. Thus, this can be a reasonable option for carefully selected patients.^[4,6]

The most widely used NIV modality is positive airway pressure ventilation provided by a mask (interface). This modality is mainly indicated in chronic alveolar hypoventilation,^[7,8] having proved useful for cases of chronic respiratory insufficiency (CRI) worsening^[9-15] and also in some cases of ARF.^[16-19] It is also useful to avoid ETI and shorten invasive ventilation time.^[20,21] Furthermore, this technique should be considered especially in patients in whom ETI is not indicated due to their underlying condition.^[6,22] There are many published studies on NIV effectiveness in adult patients with ARF in order to avoid ETI and reduce mortality.^[23,24] However, its role in pediatric ARF has not been conclusively defined yet.^[25]

The major limitation of NIV in pediatric ARF arises when selecting the right device for the application. In pediatrics, specific NIV ventilators are the most commonly used. However, due to their low usage rate specifically in pediatrics, these devices are not always available at every PICU or there are not enough, thus reducing their use. Modern conventional ventilators can provide specific NIV modes with automatic air-leak compensation.^[26] They can be an available and efficient alternative for NIV in pediatric

ARF. The aim of this study is to evaluate the usefulness of a conventional volumetric ventilator with NIV modes in pediatric ARF treatment.

METHODS

A prospective non controlled clinical study was carried out in children admitted to our PICU who were treated by NIV, over a 3-year period. The PICU is a 6-bed multivalent unit at a tertiary university hospital. The study was approved by the Institutional Review Board, and informed parental written consent was obtained. We applied NIV to ARF pediatric patients, aged 1 month to 16 years old, when the attending pediatric intensive care physician thought that the patient was likely to require ETI^[6,27] ARF was defined by the following clinical and/or gasometric criteria:

1. Increased respiratory rate for their age^[28] and moderate to severe respiratory distress signs, reaching > 4 in Clinical Score applied (Table 1), and/or
2. Hypoxemic ARF (type I): $\text{PaO}_2 < 60$ torr or arterial oxygen saturation (SatO_2) $< 90\%$ with $\text{FiO}_2 > 0,5$ ^[29] and/or
3. Hypercapnic ARF or a mixed one (type II): plus $\text{pH} < 7.35$ with $\text{PaCO}_2 > 50$ torr.^[25,29]

The postextubation ARF was defined as the clinical appearance of ARF immediately after extubation, according to the above criteria.

For acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS) and pneumonia diagnosis, the criteria followed by the American-European Consensus on ARDS^[30] and CDC^[31,32] was used respectively. The exclusion criteria for NIV treatment are available in Table 2.^[3,26,33-35]

A volumetric ventilator with specific NIV mode was used (Evita 2 Dura, Dräger Medical, Lübeck, Germany) with active humidification in all cases (Fisher and Paykel Healthcare, Auckland, New Zealand). The ventilator program includes air leakage compensation. The inspiratory trigger was a flow trigger set at the most sensitive value

without auto-triggering. Expiration was allowed by inspiratory flow decrease or after a set inspiratory time. The initial ventilation mode was different depending severity of pathology. Continuous positive airway pressure with pressure support (CPAP+PS) was used in postextubation ARF and in type I (mild to moderate), and bi-level positive airway pressure with pressure support (BIPAP+PS) was used in the rest of cases, as well as in patients treated initially with CPAP+PS whose evolution was not favourable. The non-vented oronasal face mask used in the current study was the Mirage model (Resmed, Poway, CA), Performatrack (Respironics, Murrysville, PA) or Hans Rudolph masks (Hans Rudolph Inc, Kansas City, Missouri). In order to minimize skin damage, we placed hydrophilic material (Comfeel[®], Coloplast, Humlebaek, Denmark) on the bridge of the nose and also over the area most exposed to friction. [6,21] In addition, alternating face mask models was also done relieving the support area. Dipotassium clorazepate (0.5-1 mg/kg/day) or Midazolam (0.05-0.1 mg/kg/hrs) was administered to all patients to improve mask tolerance and adaptation to MV, according to medical criteria.

Nasogastric tube (NGT) decompression was used according to attending pediatrician's criteria. Enteral feedings were not commenced until the need for intubation was ruled out. Oral feeding was started when patient improvement made intermittent NIV feasible.

We studied age, sex, underlying condition, cause and type of ARF, Pediatric Logistic Organ Dysfunction score (PELOD)^[36] and Pediatric Risk of Mortality III score (PRISM III)^[37] during the first 24 hours, ventilation mode and the initial and highest parameter values. The following measures were taken to evaluate the initial evolution in the first 24 hours:

1. Clinical assessment: respiratory work was evaluated based on the clinical score in table 1 at 0, 2 and 6 hours. Respiratory rate, heart rate and blood

pressure data were collected at the beginning and then again after 2-4, 6, and 24 hours.

2. pH, pCO₂, SatO₂ and FiO₂ were collected at the beginning and then again after 2-4 and 24 hours. Capillary samples were taken (arterialized blood by heating the peripheral extremity), because of not having initial arterial canalization in most patients. SatO₂ was measured by pulse oximetry with Masimo technology ® (Radical, Datascope, Irvine, CA). The oxygen was administered by Venturi mask, reservoir mask or nasal prongs before starting NIV. When nasal prongs were used, the FiO₂ was calculated according to the following formula: $FiO_2 = 20 + 4 \times \text{oxygen flow in L/min.}$ ^[38] Once the NIV is placed, the FiO₂ levels are measured by MV.

Thoracic radiography was performed before and after 24 hours and was evaluated by a pediatric radiologist who was not familiar with the patient's clinical evolution.

Duration of NIV, stay time in PICU and technical complications were evaluated. Treatment failure was defined as withdrawal due to poor tolerance and/or inability to stabilize the progression of respiratory failure and requiring ETI.^[39] The maximal inspiratory pressure did not exceed 25 cmH₂O.^[33,40,41] The attending pediatric intensive care physicians indicated ETI when clinical and gasometric stabilization was not achieved despite the increase in respiratory assistance. ETI was also indicated if exclusion criteria emerged during treatment (Table 2).

We compared the evolution of patients with immunosuppression (IS) and psychomotor delay to the whole series, taking into account all the parameters studied.

Statistical analysis: The SPSS statistic package 14.0 for Windows was used. ANOVAs designs were used for continuous variables between subjects and T tests for related values. Repeated measures designs were also used. Mauchly test of sphericity was used in Repeated Measures ANOVA. In case of non-compliance, Pillai's Trace

test was used. In multiple comparisons, the Bonferroni adjustment procedure was used for Type I error. The Wilcoxon matched-pairs ranks test for related values and the Kruskal-Wallis test for group comparison were used to compare ordinal variables. Fisher's exact test was applied to dichotomous variables and Ji-square for 2x3 tables. A *p* value of 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

NIV was used in 32 ARF episodes of 26 patients, 19 boys and 7 girls, aged 1 month to 16 years old (7.9 ± 5.2 yrs average). Patients' main characteristics are described in Table 3. The technique was used 3 times in one patient and twice in 4 patients. The most common cause of ARF was pneumonia in 15 cases (46.8%), followed by ARDS in 7 cases (21.8%), asthmatic episode in 5 (15.6%), postextubation ARF in 5 (15.6%). PELOD mortality risk was $12.4\% \pm 24\%$ (range, 0-84%). The PRISM III mortality score was 12.4 ± 7.7 (range, 1-28). In the initial radiograph, prior to NIV, only one quadrant was affected in 1 case (2.7%), 2 quadrants were affected in 16 cases (50%), 3 quadrants in 2 cases (5.5%) and 4 quadrants in 7 cases (21.8%). The radiograph was normal in 6 cases (18.7%), 5 suffered postextubation ARF and one had bronchiolitis.

Tolerance was good despite the initial agitation in the youngest children. Moreover, none of them required withdrawal of the technique. Anxiolytics or sedatives were administered to all patients, Dipotassium clorazepate in 15 cases and continuous perfusion with Midazolam in 17 cases. The initial and highest NIV parameter values are listed in Table 4.

There was a progressive clinical improvement score, reaching significant values both between the beginning and after 2 hours of NIV (6.3 ± 1.9 vs 4.3 ± 1.7 , $p < 0.001$), and between 2 and 6 hours of NIV (4.3 ± 1.7 vs 3.4 ± 1.7 , $p = 0.001$). A significant

improvement in respiratory and heart rate, pH, pCO₂ and SatO₂ was found at 2-4 hours after NIV initiation. This improvement was maintained throughout the study (Figures 1, 2 and 3). The FiO₂ was significantly lower at 24 hours (Figure 3).

The radiological evolution of the 6 patients with initial normal radiograph did not show alterations. For the rest, radiographic improvement was observed in 17 cases (65%) after 24 hours. None of these cases required ETI. The improvement in upper and front segments was clearer. Progression of lower lobes was slower.

In 18 cases, decompressive NGT was used during NIV therapy, subsequently used for enteric feeding in 7. Two patients had gastrostomy. Oral feeds were initiated in 7 cases when intermittent NIV therapy was tolerated.

Patients with NGT decompression, had a significantly higher mortality risk. (PELOD 19 ± 29.6 vs 3.6 ± 7 , $p < 0.05$). No differences were observed in respiratory assistance or in other evaluated parameters.

The duration of NIV treatment was 85.4 ± 62.8 hours (range, 2-216 hours). Patients who developed postextubation ARF needed less NIV time (17.2 ± 14.5 vs 100.2 ± 59.3 hours, $p < 0.001$). In seven patients, NIV was applied intermittently after initial improvement. Only 2 patients with previous CRI, needed respiratory support after discharge from the hospital (Table 3). One patient was discharged home with NIV after being admitted a second time. The third ARF episode was successfully treated with our conventional ventilator (Table 3).

Most complications were minor and related to interface, and therefore did not lead to ventilation withdrawal. The most frequent complications were mild erosion and irritative dermatitis on the bridge of the nose (11 cases). Only 1 of them required adhesiolysis and surgical suture. Three patients suffered from conjunctivitis. There were no cases of bronchoaspiration, barotrauma or gastric distension.

Four cases (12.5%) required intubation, after 3, 24, 60, and 83 hours after starting NIV treatment (Table 3). The cause of ARF was a serious ARDS (PaO₂/FiO₂

postintubation: 100.1 ± 16.8 torr). These patients required more ventilatory assistance before and after intubation (Table 4). The time of MV was 15.8 ± 5.1 days.

The mortality risk (PELOD) of the IS group was 27.5 ± 34.5 %. When comparing the evolution of this group to the rest of the series, we observed that PRISM III mortality score was significantly higher (17 ± 6.9 vs 10 ± 6.9 , $p=0.027$), required more hemodynamic support ($8/8$ vs $2/22$, $p<0.001$) and ETI ($3/8$ vs $1/23$, $p=0.014$). No differences were observed in respiratory assistance or in the rest of the analyzed parameters.

In the group of patients with psychomotor delay, ARF type II was the most frequent ($9/12$ vs $5/20$, $p=0.01$), the initial values of pH and $p\text{CO}_2$ were clinically and statistically more altered (7.25 ± 0.12 vs 7.38 ± 0.08 , $p<0.003$ and 71.6 ± 19.1 vs 44.5 ± 12.3 torr, $p<0.002$ respectively). They required BIPAP+PS more frequently ($12/12$ vs $13/20$, $p=0.029$) and suffered more complications related to interface ($8/12$ vs $5/20$, $p=0.02$). Seven of those cases (patients 2, 4, 8, 26) had limited resuscitation status. Despite this the evolution was favourable.

Length of stay in the PICU was 14.2 ± 11 days. Those who required intubation had a significantly longer stay (21.8 ± 5.6 vs 13.4 ± 11.3 , $p<0.005$). None of these patients died during hospital stay.

DISCUSSION

Currently, experience in the application of NIV in pediatric ARF is still quite limited. Most papers are retrospective studies^[6,27,42-45] and/or short series.^[14,46-48] Establishing a selection of patients likely to benefit from this technique has not yet been determined,^[33] thus restricting its use. In our opinion, this may be caused in part by a preferential use of NIV specific ventilators with limited availability. Furthermore, many of these devices do not have an inner oxygen mixer, so they are less suitable for hypoxemic ARF. For these reason conventional ventilators with NIV mode could

efficiently solve this serious problem. In our series, like in two other recent studies,^[27,49] the use of this conventional ventilator has proved its usefulness for pediatric ARF treatment. Our results show a significant improvement in the clinical, gasometrical and radiological evolution, lower complications rates and a high success rate in the application of NIV. It should be pointed out that both clinical and gasometric improvement took place within the first hours of applying this technique and this improvement was maintained throughout the first 24 hours. Moreover, in our patients the use of NIV did not worsen prognosis in patients who required ETI.

Selection of interface is a key aspect in the overall success of NIV.^[35,43] Although, due to its better tolerance a preference for nasal masks has been described,^[25,33,50] we used oronasal masks because they avoid mouth leaks and improve ventilation and pressurization, thus making them more efficient in the ARF.^[43,50]

We agree with other authors^[21] the importance of having different sizes and models of masks, so as to vary the pressure points as outlined above. This way, tolerance is improved and the risk of local complications is reduced when the application of NIV extends. Our results show that changing masks is especially important in patients with psychomotor delay. As in other studies,^[21,33,49,51] we used sedation to improve tolerance. Patients did not experience any complications. According to our results, indication for decompressive NGT depends on the severity of the patient's condition and not to the ventilation assistance since gastric distension is unlikely to occur with pressure less than < 25 cmH₂O.^[33,34]

According to our experience, the most efficient NIV mode in pediatric ARF is BIPAP + PS and must be tested early, before the patient requires intubation. When comparing the ventilatory parameters used by other authors, we observed that PEEP/EPAP used was similar but with slightly higher PIP/IPAP values.^[6,27,39,44,52] However, more information on the severity of the patient's condition is needed to make a proper comparison. Only the most recent studies provide this information, showing

our patient's high mortality risk.^[27,49,53] In addition, available data on the severity of ARF are scarce. Initial radiological data were not found and only a subjective clinical scoring system ^[39] or a specific asthma scoring system ^[53] was applied. Although the synthesis scores of Silverman and Wood-Downes that we propose have not been validated, we believe it can be applied to any type of ARF by using general failure rate parameters of both scores. Likewise, the clinical evolution can be evaluated objectively by considering all the parameters easily evaluated by different observers, therefore making it useful for establishing comparisons.

The etiology of ARF in our series was similar to the one found in other studies. The most frequent cause of ARF being pneumonia^[6,39,43,49,52] and ARDS was the main cause of technique failure.^[27] Although NIV failed in 4 patients with ARDS, ETI was avoided in 3 other patients. Moreover, NIV time varied greatly in those patients that needed ETI, being more than 24 h in 3 of them. These patients did not show radiological improvement and required major respiratory assistance (Table 4) and MV time. These facts suggest that intubation was due to disease progression and not to an inappropriate initial indication of NIV. We agree with other authors^[55] and consider that NIV should be tested early in patients with hypoxemic ARF. This is especially important in IS patients due to poor prognosis after ETI, with mortality rates ranging from 50% to 100% in adults^[16,17,56-58] and children.^[47,59,60] Although 3 out of 4 patients that required ETI belonged to this group, intubation could have been avoided in the other 5, surviving all of them. In our opinion, it is possible that these results are related, in part, to the early respiratory support.

NIV has also proved especially useful in the group of patients with psychomotor delay, most with a CRI grade variable. Despite the greater initial respiratory involvement, the evolution was favourable in all cases, including those in which ETI may not be considered appropriate by family and physicians.^[6]

In conclusion, NIV can be successfully applied to infants and children with acute respiratory failure by means of this modern conventional ventilator with NIV mode in the setting of a pediatric intensive care unit. It must be considered particularly in children with post-extubation ARF and patients whose underlying condition warrants avoidance of intubation.

According to Elliot^[62] “there is much to be gained and little to be lost trying NIV, but then again, these patients should be carefully monitored by a motivated and well-trained critical care team because their conditions can deteriorate rapidly, and the risk of a delayed intubation is not acceptable”.

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Clinical signs	Score		
	0	1	2
Intercostal/sternal retractions	no	Costal	costal+sternal
Thoraco-abdominal dissociation	no	Moderate	High
Nasal Flaring	no	Slight	High
Expiratory groan	no	auscultation	Yes
Cyanosis (Sat. O ₂)	no (>92%)	with air (<92%)	with FiO ₂ >0, 4 (<92%)
Conscience level	normal	depression/restlessness	lethargy/maximum restlessness
Score: <4: slight, 4-6: moderate, >6: severe			

Table 1. Clinical score: it was applied a synthesis of Silverman and Wood-Downes test. Silverman's test was used, unifying the evolution of the costal and sternal retractions as a unique parameter, and we included the evaluation of conscience level and of cyanosis of Wood-Downes score. This last parameter was evaluated by pulse oximetry, instead of PO₂ and clinical evaluation.

- Patients younger than 1 month
- Patients who need immediate ETI
- Inability to protect the airway
- Hemodynamic instability (refractory at volemic expansion > 60 mL/kg and Dopamin > 10 mcg/kg/min).
- Malformation, traumatismos or facial burns
- Severe digestive hemorrhage
- Undrained pneumothorax
- Severe upper airway obstruction
- Abundant respiratory secretions
- Complete absence of collaboration

Table 2. Exclusion criteria to NIV treatment.

Cases	Patients	Age (years)	Underlying condition	Cause of ARF	Type of ARF	PELOD% / PRISM III	Chest Rx#	Outcome	Hours NIV therapy
1	1	8,3	Psychomotor delay	Postextubation ARF	II	1/9	0	Success	32
2	1	9,9	Psychomotor delay	Postextubation ARF	clinical	-	0	Success	4
3	2	15,8	Down syndrome	Bilateral pneumonia	II	20,8/18	2	Success	216
4	2	15,9	Down syndrome	Lung atelectasia	II	1,7/17	2	Success	72
5	3	13,2	Obesity	Bilateral pneumonia + asthma	I	0/13	2	Success	74
6	3	14,7	Obesity	Bilateral pneumonia + asthma	I	0/6	2	Success	156
7	4	2,3	Psychomotor delay + CRI (a)	Bilateral pneumonia	II	1,3/21	4	Success	96
8	5	3	AML (b) + IS (c)	ARDS (d)	II	84/28	4	Intubation	24
9	6	13,8	Previous severe TBI (e)	Lung atelectasia	I	1/12	2	Success	27
10	7	12,5	ALL (f) + IS	ARDS	I	1/15	2	Success	168
11	8	6	Psychomotor delay +CRI	Bilateral pneumonia	II	16,2/16	4	Success	67
12	8	6,8	Psychomotor delay +CRI	Bilateral pneumonia	II	16,2/21	2	Success (+)	100
13	8	7	Psychomotor delay +CRI	Pneumonia	II	1/22	1	Success (+)	60
14	9	12,4	Psychomotor delay	Bilateral pneumonia	II	0,1/5	2	Success	31
15	10	2,3	Severe neutropenia	ARDS	II	79,6/25	2	Intubation	3
16	11	5,8	Psychomotor delay	Pneumonia	II	20,8/19	2	Success	96
17	12	12,6	-	ARDS	I	79,6/17	2	Success	10
18	13	5,7	Tracheal resection	Postextubation ARF	clinical	0/0	0	Success	2
19	14	10,3	Burkitt's lymphoma + IS	ARDS	I	16,2/22	3	Success	72
20	15	13,8	Down syndrome + Tracheal resection	Postextubation ARF	II	1/7	0	Success	16
21	16	13,8	ALL+IS	Pneumonia / ALI (g)	clinical	20,8/21	4	Success	95
22	17	13	-	Pneumonia + pleural effusions	II	1/8	3	Success	120
23	18	11,8	T-Cell Lymphoma	ARDS	II	16,2/11	4	Intubation	83
24	19	9,2	Spinal cord atrophy +CRI	Pneumonia + asthmatic episode	I	1/3	2	Success (+)	144
25	20	1,5	Immunodeficiency	Pneumonia	clinical	1/8	2	Success	117
26	21	4	ALL +IS	ALI + Interstitial pneumonia	clinical		4	Success	164
27	22	1,8	Bronchopulmonary dysplasia	Asthmatic episode	I	1/3	2	Success	144
28	23	0,2	-	Pneumonia	clinical	0/2	2	Success	52
29	24	2,3	OSAS (h)	ARDS	II	1/3	4	Intubation	60
30	24	2,3	OSAS	Postextubation ARF	I	0/2	0	Success	32
31	25	0,08	-	Bronchiolitis	II	0/10	0	Success	8
32	26	0,7	Psychomotor delay + CRI	Pneumonia + asthmatic episode	I	0/7	2	Success	216

Table 3: Main characteristics of patients. (#) Quadrant affectation in thoracic radiography; (a) CRI: chronic respiratory insufficiency; (b) AML: acute myeloid leukemia; (c) IS: immunosuppressed; (d) ARDS: acute respiratory distress syndrome; (e) TBI: trauma brain injury; (f) ALL: acute lymphoblastic leukaemia; (g) ALI: acute lung injury; (h) OSAS: obstructive sleep apnoea syndrome; success (+): home NIV.

	INITIAL NIV ASSISTANCE	HIGHEST ASSISTANCE		
		All NIV patients	NIV failure patients	Post-intubation
NIV MODE (n)	CPAP+PS (13) BIPAP+PS (19)	CPAP+PS (7) BIPAP+PS (25)	BIPAP+PS (4)	CMV (4)
FiO₂	0.5 ± 0.2 (range 0.3-0.9)	0.5 ± 0.2 (range 0.3-1)	0.7 ± 0.2 (range 0.6-0.9)	0.8 ± 0.1 (range 0.75-1)
PIP (cmH ₂ O)	16.8 ± 3 (range 14-23)	18.5 ± 2.7 (range 15-25)	20.7 ± 1.2 (range 20-23)	35 ± 10.1 (range 28-50)
PEEP (cmH ₂ O)	5 ± 0.8 (range 4-6)	5.7 ± 1.1 (range 4-9)	7 ± 2 (range 5-9)	9.8 ± 2.1 (range 8-12)
PS (cmH ₂ O)	9.6 ± 2.3 (range 5-15)	10.5 ± 2.7 (range 5-18)	12.3 ± 0.6 (range 10-13)	-
MP (cmH ₂ O)	8.1 ± 1.5 (range 5-11)	9.2 ± 2 (range 6-14)	12.3 ± 1.5 (range 11-14)	18.8 ± 2.2 (range 16-21)

Table 4. Initial and highest assistance. CMV: controlled mechanical ventilation; PIP: peak inspiratory pressure; PEEP: positive end-expiratory pressure; PS: pressure support over PEEP; MP: mean pressure.

Figure 1. Heart rate (HR) and respiratory rate (RR) evolution. A significant reduction in both took place at 2-4 hours after beginning NIV treatment. This improvement was maintained throughout the first 6 to 24 hours (0 hours vs later $p < 0.001$ for both parameters).

Figure 2. Evolution of pH and pCO₂. NIV produced a quick improvement both in pH as well as pCO₂ which was maintained throughout the first 24 hours (0 hours vs later $p < 0.038$ and $p < 0.016$ respectively)

Figure 3. Oxygen saturation (SatO₂) and FiO₂ evolution. SatO₂ showed a quick improvement during the first 2-4 hours. This improvement was maintained throughout the first 24 hours (0 hours vs later p < 0.001). FiO₂ was significantly lower 24 hours after initiating NIV treatment (24 hours vs previous times p < 0.017).